

BASIS OF EMERGENCE OF INTERNATIONAL ISLAMIC FINANCIAL ORGANIZATIONS

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Abstract: This article discusses the concept and essence of Islamic finance, including Islamic banking. Also, the necessity and gradual development of this financial system in foreign countries is analyzed using the experience of a number of countries. International Islamic financial organizations are also considered in the article.

Key words: Aqidah, ethics, jurisprudence, Islamic finance, Islamic banking, Islamic branches, AAOIFI

INTRODUCTION

Islamic scholars have divided the Islamic religion into three major branches, which are Aqeedah (rules of faith and trust), Akhlaq (rules of morals and manners) and Fiqh (rules of rights and obligations). Fiqh, in turn, is divided into the right of worship (regulates the relationship between people and God, that is, the rules of worship) and the right of interaction (regulates the relationship between people). The law of exchange regulates social, criminal, administrative, family, political and economic rules. Islamic finance, in particular, Islamic banking belongs to the department that regulates relations in the economic sphere [1].

LITERATURE REVIEW

After the Muslim countries became colonies of Western countries, interest-based banking systems began to appear in them by the end of the 19th century and the beginning of the 20th century. Therefore, Sharia scholars in these countries emphasized the need to introduce an alternative banking and financial system that meets Sharia requirements for Muslim societies and started practical work on this. In particular, in 1890, an organization providing interest-free financing was established in India. Later, in 1923, an institution called Anjuman Imdad-e-Bahmi Qardh Bila Sud (Interest Free Credit Society) was established in Hyderabad.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

After the establishment of the state of Pakistan, in 1950, the first Islamic bank was established in this country, and this bank started to provide interest-free banking services such as muroba and wakala (agency).

In 1963, an Islamic bank operating in accordance with Sharia rules was founded in Egypt through the establishment of a local fund known as Mit Ghamr. "Pilgrims Fund Corporation" was established in order to provide financial support for Muslims in performing Hajj in Malaysia. In 1969, this corporation was incorporated into the Pilgrims Management and Fund Board, known as Tabung Haji.

Malaysia was the first country that took the initiative to systematically study the issue of establishing a modern financial system (dualistic system) that complies with the requirements of Sharia, and until today it occupies a leading position in the market of Islamic financial instruments.

If we pay attention to the experience of the countries of the world, the introduction of Islamic finance, in particular, the system of Islamic banks, was carried out in the following three directions.

1. The monistic model of the transition to Islamic finance is considered, in which all financial institutions were massively transferred to the Islamic banking-finance system, and traditional banking was completely abolished. It is believed that Iran, Pakistan, and Sudan have carried out this experience.

This way has created various difficulties for the above countries in extinguishing foreign debts, and because this method has been switched to administrative methods at once, problems have arisen in the management and control of the system. As a result, Pakistan allowed the traditional financing system to operate simultaneously in the country.

As a result of striving to idealize Islamic finance, Iran has become a country where fake Islamic finance is practiced. Only Sudan has been able to succeed in this system by recognizing the mistakes and shortcomings and regularly correcting them.

2. A dualistic model of transition to Islamic finance, in which traditional and Islamic financial institutions operate in parallel in the same country. The activities of Islamic financial institutions are regulated by separate legislation, and Islamic finance is gradually developed based on market demand. This system was first introduced by Malaysia, the United Arab Emirates, Kuwait, and Bahrain, and now it is being implemented in Turkey, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, and Tajikistan.

3. The third direction is the way of the countries that are loyal to the traditional financial system practiced in the West, in which a special position for Islamic financial institutions is not recognized (UK, USA, Russia).

Islamic banking and finance began to spread widely not only in Islamic

countries, but also in Western countries. In particular, "Islamic Banking International Holding" (Luxembourg) in 1978; "Dar-al-mal-al-Islami" (Geneva) in 1981; In 1982, Al-Baraka Group and the Danish International Islamic Bank (Denmark); In 1983, "Islamic Finance House" (London) was established. In addition to the institutions mentioned above, there are several world-renowned international conventional banks that offer Islamic banking services, including Chase Manhattan, Citibank, HSBC, Union Bank of Switzerland, BNP-Paribas. , "Standard Chartered" and other banks[4].

CONCLUSION

To summarize the above, the development of Islamic finance was implemented in the form of the introduction of a monistic and dualistic system. During this period, many mistakes and shortcomings were made and corrected, adapted to modern financial relations, standardization and control at the international level was ensured. In general, until now, valuable experience has been created for the use of Uzbekistan.

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